

RELATIONS WITH BUDDHIST MONKS AND RELIGIOUS COMMUNITIES DURING THE ERA OF AMIR TEMUR

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the relations between Buddhist monks and religious communities during the era of Amir Temur based on historical sources. The study highlights the activities of religious communities living in the territories of the Timurid Empire and neighboring Buddhist regions, as well as their participation in political, cultural, and diplomatic relations. It also examines Amir Temur's approach to managing a multi-confessional society, his policy toward representatives of the Buddhist religion, and the practical manifestations of the principles of religious tolerance.*

Keywords: *Amir Temur, Buddhism, monks, communities, tolerance, diplomacy, religion, politics, Timurids, confession.*

According to historical sources, Amir Temur maintained practical and diplomatic relations with representatives of various religions while simultaneously ensuring the political interests of his state. In particular, the study of interreligious relations during the Timurid period is of great importance in the study of relations with regions where Buddhism was spread, as well as the activities of Buddhist monks and religious communities. Buddhism was one of the widespread religious teachings in the Middle Ages in Eastern Turkestan, Mongolia, Tibet, China, and other regions, and its representatives occupied a certain place in international trade, cultural exchange, and diplomatic relations. Amir Temur's relations with Buddhist monks and religious communities were closely linked not only to religious but also to political and cultural processes. Through these relationships, one can observe certain aspects of communication, interaction, and cooperation between different civilizations. Therefore, the study of this issue serves to a deeper understanding of the foreign policy of the Timurid state, the principles of religious tolerance and the history of interfaith relations.

In turn, the Chinese side, fearing Amir Timur's successes, tried to establish good relations with him. The main reason for this was the fear of an alliance with the Mongols, who, in alliance with the ruler of Samarkand, might attack China. Therefore, there is every reason to conclude that the Chinese (Min) government sought to support the forces opposed to Amir Timur. In addition to the Mongols, there was the Tibetan problem for the Ming dynasty, and Tibetan Buddhist monks had great influence at the court of the Mongol Yuan dynasty. In turn, the Mongols provided sufficient support to the monks of Lamaism in Tibet.

The coronation of the Mongol rulers of the Yuan dynasty was conducted under the leadership of Buddhist priests. The coronation of the last Yuan Emperor, Toghhan Timur, in 1331 was performed by Rangjung Dorje, the leader of the Karmapa sect, which broke away from Buddhism's Lamaism. Based on information in historical literature, it can be concluded that representatives of the Karmapa sect, known as the Black Caps, also exerted significant influence in Transoxiana. Even after the death of Amir Timur, in order to ensure the security of the Ming dynasty, the fifth black-caped lama, Karmapa Choypel Zangpo (1384-1415), was appointed as the head of the Ming dynasty. Invited to the Ming court (1407), he was attempted to be held in China as an honorary hostage. Although this monk's journey to China and the political aspects of the visit are not covered, Tibetan chronicles mention that he went to the Chinese court to lead religious ceremonies. If we pay attention to the years of this priest's life, there is reason to believe that he was at the palace of Amir Timur. For this reason, although the Mongols were expelled from China, the influence of the representatives of Genghis Khan's empire was still strong, and in Tibet, although the power of the clergy was abolished after the fall of the Yuan dynasty and the influence of local provincial governors increased, it is noted in historical documents that during the reign of Zhi Yuanzhan, Tibetans repeatedly invaded the territories bordering China.

By this time, the rule of the clergy in Tibet had been abolished, and secular feudal lords had come to power. The new dynasty, the Pagmodupa family, seized power in Tibet, and during the reign of Taistu Janchub Chjalsan (1302-1373), several raids on China were carried out for the purpose of obtaining booty. Nevertheless, the Chinese Ming dynasty traded horses for tea with Tibet and feared that this trade would cease. Emperor Zhi Yuanzhan established cha-ke-si, or tea trading posts, on the borders. These branches primarily ensured the neutrality of Tibet in the struggle against the Mongols and allowed for the

purchase of horses in battles that the Chinese army lacked. There are sufficient grounds to believe that Amir Timur had his own plans regarding Tibet. It is possible that Amir Temur ordered a portion of the population of Mawarannahr to settle in Tibet and to keep himself informed about the existing political, economic, and social relations there. Because to this day, representatives of the Turkic Solor clan live in Tibet, and in their memory, there is a legend related to their arrival in Tibet from Samarkand during the time of Amir Temur. This serves as a basis for the conclusion that relations existed between Tibet and the empire of Amir Temur.

Diplomatic relations with Tibet after Amir Temur date back to the reign of Mirzo Ulugbek; during the winter of 1421–1422, ambassadors from Tibet and China visited Mirzo Ulugbek in Bukhara. However, information about the goals and directions of these ambassadors has not been preserved in the sources. If we analyze the information provided in historical literature, the period of patronage and inclination of the first emperors of the Ming dynasty to Tibetan Buddhism ended at this time, and Tibetan Buddhists were forced to turn their attention again to the north - the Mongols and Oirats, who were their allies during the Yuan dynasty. It can be concluded that these processes were sent by representatives of the numerous Buddhist sects in Tibet, or by the current ruling dynasty of Pagmodupa, whose main stronghold was the Uy region of Tibet, or by the Rinpun dynasty, whose main stronghold was the province of Zan. This is because the Tibetan chronicles compiled by the clergy contain no information regarding the embassy sent to Ulugh Beg's palace. Based on the analysis of data from the work "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bahrain," it can be concluded that the ambassadors returned to China and Tibet after staying in Bukhara from January to February 6, 1421.

In conclusion, it can be said that during the era of Amir Temur, relations with Buddhist monks and religious communities developed in close connection with the political, economic, and cultural interests of the state. Relations with Buddhist communities within the Timurid Empire and in neighboring territories contributed to the expansion of trade relations, the development of intercultural dialogue, and the strengthening of international diplomatic relations. Amir Temur's pragmatic and balanced policy toward representatives of various religions was one of the important factors in ensuring stability in a multi-confessional society. Therefore, the study of contacts with Buddhist monks and religious communities allows for a deeper understanding of interreligious

relations, religious tolerance, and the principles of state governance during the Timurid era.

References:

1. Barthold V.V. Ulugbek and His Time. Petrograd, 1918. – 160 p.
2. Barthold V. V. Essay on the History of Semirechye // Works. Volume II, Part 1. – Moscow: Publishing House of Oriental Literature, 1963. - 1020 p.
3. Vostrikov A.I. Tibetan Historical Literature. – M.: Approved for publication by the Institute of the Peoples of Asia of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1962. - 426 p.
4. Yazdi, Sharafuddin Ali. Zafarioma // Author of the preface, translations, comments and indicators and preparers for publication: A.Ahmad, H.Bobobekov: Responsible editor B.Eshpulatov. Publications and a group of printers: I. Shogulomov et al. // - T.: Sharq, 1997. - Б. 217-218. - 384 p. + Appendix 16.
5. Kadyrbaev A.Sh. Mongols, Chinese, and Europeans in Tibet (1368-1644). // Bulletin of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2018. No. 1. – P. 121-129.
6. Kitinov B.U. The Buddhist factor in the political and ethnic history of the Oirats (mid-15th century – 1771). // Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Historical Sciences. - MOSCOW, 2020. – 546 p.

